

THE IMPORTANCE OF USING INNOVATIVE METHODS DURING THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSON

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ABSTRACT

This paper analyses the revolutionary and quite fascinating techniques we have in instructing English language. We may additionally have a range of instructing techniques in between standard and modern. Everybody has their own understanding and conclusions on instructing English language. But this paper portrays combining these two types how we can make our instructing very effective. We have been absolutely bounded with ordinary methods of educating and grasp the place the present-day newbies felt uncomfortable a bit. Learner's thought will never be static it is ever developing and ever changing. Whatever the educating methodology can be, however teaching must be learner's centered. However, this paper scrutinizes the difference between regular and sensible teaching and thereafter learning. This treatise practically examines that how rookies are being affected by way of the traditional strategies of educating as well, without it has portrayed that how rookies assume educating and studying process. There has been a misunderstanding between standard methods and practical techniques always. Somehow instructors and learners should agree each other in order to fill the gap between the generations of these methods.

Keywords: method, modern, atmosphere, traditional, CLT (Communicative language teaching), ELT (English language teaching).

INTRODUCTION

The teaching of overseas languages are achieved common or barely teacher centered strategies rather than cutting-edge student- centered purposes and strategies while the transmission of knowledge and information has been realized with the ordinary shape of lectures or discussions requiring bodily presence of both scholar and the teacher. Furthermore, the educating techniques used may vary in terms of the degree of have an impact on on energetic learning.

The intention of this article is to analyze the normal and progressive strategies for teaching and mastering the foreign language as nicely as to disclose and show a set of effective pedagogical prerequisites for gaining knowledge of languages. We can flip our interest to the complete description of the key words, “traditional methodology” and “modern methodology”.

One of the aims of any methodology in overseas language educating is to enhance the foreign language capacity of the student.

1. TRADITIONAL METHOD

Traditional methodology is based generally on a reduction of the integrated process of using a foreign language. Very normal feature of normal methodology is the trainer – dominated interaction. The teaching is deeply teacher-centered. Unlike traditional methodology, cutting-edge methodology is lots greater student-centered. The teacher’s main position is to help gaining knowledge of to happen, which includes involving students in what is going on by enabling them to work at their very own speed, by way of not giving long explanations, by encouraging them to participate, talk, interact, and do things.

This technique is very teacher-dominated. The magnificent accountability is put on the shoulders of teachers. He/ She provides mass of information, alongside he/she gives amazing deal of duties which are completely associated with translation, texts or new phrases and asking them in turn. Some students replicate on consideration on that in everyday method of education, where instructors serve as the furnish of grasp at the equal time college students come to be very passive receivers.

Advantages of traditional teaching method:

- Teacher supervise the class, giving and impacting systematic knowledge, academic opinion with speculate philosophy, conducts class, giving a long lecture.
- Students receive wisdom and power that is good for the development of their IQ.
- Teacher is able to give whole or broad and deep information on the given topic throughout the lesson.
- Teacher can change his/her teaching style in accordance of their aptitude for a better explanation.
- Another big advantage is face to face simulative factor for students’ comprehensive quality. Where is lively atmosphere and interaction with human and between people, there is a big prospect of progress.
- Comparing to others, the traditional teaching is more direct and effective method, as teacher control and inspire students effectively when the student encounter problems or arise conflicts, they take flexible teaching method adjusting the content

according to actual requirement. Learners imitate their teachers, because teachers are always in the center of attention and their academic level have great impact on students.

Briefly, the traditional approach shows language primarily from the rule-governed point of view and concentrates on the knowledge of grammar and items of vocabulary. It is supposed that a person who knows the rules and the lexis is able to understand and speak the target language [5].

2. INNOVATIVE METHODS

Some innovations came through and lectures became more in active. So that students and professors organized their work via cooperation in the learning process.

Broughton provides that the language scholar is first-rate motivated by way of practice in which he senses the language is absolutely communicative that it is excellent to its context, that his teacher's abilities are transferring him ahead to a fuller competence in a foreign language [1, P.33.].

In a fact, students are the most active element in the process. The instructor is here not to explain however to motivate and assist college students to explore make getting to know interesting.

Jim Scrivener suggested the most famous or the most common strategies in current teaching are [2, P.12]:

- Match the words with the pictures
- Check the meaning of these words in the dictionary
- Match the words with the definitions
- Brainstorm words on a set topic
- Divide these words into two groups
- Label the items in a picture with right names
- Complete gapped sentences with words from a list
- Discuss a topic
- Say which words you expect to be in a text about

2.1. TEACHING THROUGH GAMES

This is a very interesting approach of teaching. Students and adolescents generally tend to like video games and want to play them more and more. Traditional strategies dictated for find out about and games to be separate however the truth remains that the college students have a tendency to be more fascinated in enjoying video games instead than sitting down to study. Any logical reasoning would dictate us to combine the two elements to remedy the problem. The games part of learning would assist the students preserve their pastime as the wish to win is very strong. It keeps us going and when included with unique elements of studying the mastering technique would continue almost at some stage in the day without the teens getting tired or bored of reading.

2.2. WORD GAMES

The most necessary section of any language is the vocabulary. To understand the which means of the phrases and to use them in day to day lifestyles is a very tough undertaking and video games can assist the college students overcome this difficulty. Games like scrabble, housie etc. have been designed for this specific purpose. These games are simply based on phrases and assist the students increase their vocabulary. In addition to these very simple games can be played to assist improve the phrase database of the students such as simple dictation competitions, synonym competitions, phrases puzzles, anagrams and hangman. All these games are very addictive and help a lot in improving our vocabulary as every time the student hears a new word the first query that comes up is “what is its meaning?” and in this way the vocabulary improves and most of the times we don’t even have to seek advice from the dictionary.

2.3. HELP FROM THE MULTIMEDIA

Multimedia sources like songs, movies, TV series, magazines, newspapers play a very critical position in improving our language. We don’t even realize that they have helped us. We just wake up one quality day and realize that we are better than it than we have been yesterday. Such sources can be used to help the students improve their language. But brilliant precautions ought to be taken. This approach need to be used in the final ranges of gaining knowledge of as that is the only region the place there is no scope of harm as most of the films and songs etc. use colloquial English most of the instances which is grammatically incorrect and it is very essential that the college students apprehend that fact so that they do now not use that structure of the language in their everyday usage. Apart from that this supply is very helpful as it does now not sense like education. This is some thing that the students will do in their spare time. The songs are the great way to speak how to use a language to express our feelings. Movies are a very common past time however aside from that most of the instances they are additionally very academic and educational. Also this technique appeals to the college students as most of the times they are in a position to connect with the songs and the films which assist them apprehend the meaning of expressions, utilization of tools of the language like comparisons, personifications etc. These sources help them recognize why such tools are necessary and also help them apprehend their usage. Hence this technique is once more very superb in instructing the language. Traditional strategies of studying newspapers and books, novels are also very true techniques to instruct the language. When the normal methods are modified along with some progressive ideas the complete mastering and the educating technique is enriched and guarantees a success in environment friendly learning. These are some of the innovative and innovative ways of teaching the English Language.

3.CONCLISION

In the conclusion, we can say that for innovative methodology is increased motivating than traditional methodology. Especially for children, motivation is a imperative aspect of education due to the fact there is a lot of schooling until now of them. From this it seems that each standard and organization new methodologies brings penalties with admire to levels of encyclopedic knowledge, on the other hand that modern methodology is additionally larger extremely good in encouraging teenagers to talk and in developing a extraordinarily proper mindset to the subject. Since it seems that motivation is one of the most crucial elements of children's education, we would perchance conclude that present day methodology be favored in schools, colleges, lyceums and Universities particularly.

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